

THEORETICAL BASIS AND PRACTICAL EXPRESSION OF MARKETING EFFICIENCY ASSESSMENT

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Abstract: *This article describes the methods, theoretical and practical aspects of improving the effectiveness of marketing services by evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities, as well as the effectiveness of marketing services. In addition, the article discusses the possibilities of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities by analysing the economic performance of the enterprise.*

Keywords: *marketing, marketing activities, marketing service efficiency, marketing management, methods of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities.*

In today's rapidly evolving market economy, with the rapid change of the external environment and the complexity of the market activities of enterprises, it is important to constantly monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of marketing services, including business processes, customer satisfaction, improving service quality in all areas. earns. Assessing the effectiveness of marketing in the activities of enterprises is a difficult task, the impact of the service provided to consumers through the services of the marketing department is not always measurable, and the value created does not give accurate results.

Despite the fact that marketing specialists pay enough attention to the problems of enterprise efficiency, marketing service efficiency, there is still no clearly structured models, methods and system of indicators that allow to evaluate marketing activities.

As a result of our research, considering the effectiveness of marketing activities, Peter Doyle concluded: "Efficiency links results to cost, which is an internal indicator that is easy to measure and can be improved if needed.

The concept of efficiency is related to the satisfaction of consumer needs and is an external indicator that is difficult to measure and takes a long time to implement." In addition, Peter Drucker, an economist, analyses the concept of

efficiency and compares productivity and efficiency, interpreting their essence as follows: "Productivity allows you to do everything you need, and efficiency is finding what you need."

Philip Kotler, a marketing scientist, focuses on the effectiveness of marketing activities in his research, arguing that "continuous monitoring of efficiency suggests that it is a very important process for any firm".

Based on the theory of marketing efficiency, the process of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing services is analysed in several ways. As a rule, the concepts of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities and the effectiveness of marketing services can be defined as follows: for what purpose the evaluation is carried out?; Who are the results for? where and how to use the results? and others. The concepts mentioned above are closely related and complement each other. As a result of our research and studies, scientists and researchers have proposed the following methods to determine the effectiveness of marketing activities to date:

The quality method involves the use of marketing control and audit, during which a comprehensive analysis of all threats and opportunities through the results of the SWOT analysis of the external environment of the organization, as well as the internal environment. Results-oriented marketing control and audit, analysis of the qualitative aspects of the organization's activities.

A quantitative method of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities requires a comparison with the subtraction of marketing and advertising costs from the gross profit received after marketing expenses are made, which represent the final financial results of the organization's activities.

The sociological method of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities will focus on the use of practical sociological tools - the development of a sociological research program and the conduct of research itself.

The scoring method of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities allows to determine the effectiveness of each event by assigning a certain score for each criterion, taking into account compliance with the list of criteria, the conformity of structures and processes to the marketing concept.

The regressive and correlation method is used to establish relationships between groups of variables that characterize marketing activities.

Multivariate method, factorial and cluster analysis is used to substantiate marketing decisions based on many interrelated parameters, such as determining sales of a new product based on its technical level, price, advertising costs, and marketing elements.

The statistical theory method is used to stochastically describe the attitude of consumers to changes in market conditions.

We have already covered the methods of evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities, and learned their theoretical basis. In addition, information methods in evaluating the effectiveness of marketing activities allow you to evaluate the effectiveness of marketing activities using software Sales Expert 2, Success and others, whose purpose is to collect marketing data. The information is also a necessary resource for the marketing service, providing an opportunity to analyse the level of impact on mailings, publications, advertising, workshops and customers.

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